

Increasing Student-Athletes' Awareness of Transferable Skills for Transition to Non-athletic Career Settings

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Abstract: This concept paper proposes a career intervention for collegiate student-athletes to aid in their process of transitioning to a non-athletic career setting after their exit from their sport participation in college. It aims to address the lack of awareness of this population in terms of the transferable skills which they have learned and mastered through their sport and how these skills can be useful while they navigate the world of work. The intervention will focus on creating awareness of the skills they possess, boosting their confidence that these skills make them career-ready and employable, and introducing them to career resources and learning opportunities that can help them solidify the transferable skills that they've gained through their sport. The intervention will be guided by the Life Development Intervention (LDI) model by Danish, Petitpas and Hale (1993) who recognized that there are critical life events that may prompt an athlete to transition out of sports, and it is where the utilization of their transferable skills for continued growth and successful adaptation to a new setting will be relevant. They identified a three-step process in which counselors can help influence student-athletes to recognize their skills that are acquired through sports, how they are developed in the sports context, identify settings out of sport where they have utilized those same skills and how to apply them more specifically in a non-athletic career setting. The specific strategies that will be employed to attain these targets include development of self and career exploration modules, use of Transferable Skills Inventory, workshops and learning sessions, tapping of former student-athletes as resource for career talks, exposure and participation in career events in campus, introducing them to internships and volunteer work, career mentoring and career counseling. Over-all, the intervention hopes to contribute to the career-readiness and employability of collegiate student-athletes.

Keywords: student-athletes, transferable skills, career, transition, intervention.

I. INTRODUCTION

Similar with other college students, student-athletes are expected to develop the skills needed for adulthood and for their career when they transition out of sports. Aside from maintaining good academic records to keep their scholarships and to be eligible to compete, they are confronted as well with the big challenge of preparing themselves for life after college or life after competitive sports. Balancing athletic and academic tasks is not the only responsibility that student-athletes must manage; they are also faced with the challenges of setting their future career direction and developing other basic and essential skills that every college graduate should possess to be career-ready and employable. With the growing importance attached to graduate employability nowadays, student-athletes have to maximize every learning opportunity that will allow them to be career-ready soon after college. However, this won't come easy for this special population whose time and energy in college is very much spent on year-round athletic training and tournaments and not too much on career preparation activities being offered to college students. Though academic programs will strongly promote the development of skills and attributes together with the technical know-how, it may still not be sufficient for a graduate to be work-ready and fully able to face the unpredictable and challenging work environment. The manpower demand of the industry right now is no longer

limited to hiring only those who are with academic competence, but preference is also given to those whose generic skills are adequately developed. Generic skills commonly relate to non-technical skills and capabilities or the soft and transferable skills that may make an individual secure work, become an asset to his or her employer, and take the skills from one job role to another at any stage of one's career (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2010). Simply put, being an employable graduate denotes being equipped with basic non-technical and transferable skills necessary for getting, keeping and doing well on a job. In the case of a college student-athlete, transferable athletic skills are the abstract skills learned in the sporting environment that are applicable to other facets of life or to another career (Mayocchi and Hanrahan, 2000 as cited in Rhomberg, 2021). Long-term athletic participation can facilitate the development of these skills; however, it is quite common for student-athletes to not recognize how sport-related skills are valued or can be applied in the world of work. They can understand the application of non-technical skills to succeed in their sports but may overlook how these skills could be applicable to other domains of their life especially in their possible careers in a non-sport setting. The level of involvement in athletics often limits them from seeing that the skills they've refined and mastered in a highly dynamic and competitive sporting environment can be translated into becoming valuable skills in a work environment. They identify more with their athletic identity, thus focusing more on fulfilling their athletic roles, tasks and goals than on exploring non-athletic opportunities that will allow them to discover and make use of the skills that their sport has taught them. Student-athletes are often unable or less able to gain work experience, do volunteer work or internships, or even major in their preferred area of interest during college, thus also limiting their opportunities to be aware of necessary job skills as well as the presence of transferable skills in them which they gained throughout their involvement in sports. What most student-athletes do not realize is that their sport participation and their being part of a sport team is already a valuable source of learning opportunities to form transferable skills which can already warrant the interest of employers and will eventually be useful in surviving a challenging workplace.

At some point in a student-athlete's life, they will have to find ways to cope with the loss of their athletic identity and adjust to this major change in their life. Transitioning into a non-athletic career setting can be challenging if student-athletes lack the awareness of what their transferable skills are and if these skills are relevant and useful enough to land them in an unfamiliar territory which is the workplace. This lack of awareness can negatively impact their self-perception as a potential job candidate. As Chalfin et al. (2015 as cited in Woods, 2017) posited, to be successful in this transition process, athletes must become familiar with the skills and strengths they have gained through competitive sport, build their personal brand outside of sport, and learn how to capitalize and market their transferable skills in a non-athletic career setting. To aid them in the transition process, support should be directed towards education on transferable sport skills by providing them with learning opportunities to discover what transferable skills do they possess and how these skills can be utilized in the world of work. It is in this light that this concept paper is being forwarded. It hopes to be a springboard for a career intervention that will facilitate the student-athlete's recognition of the skills they've learned and mastered through their sport which can successfully transfer to other non-athletic career settings. The effort can hopefully create a positive impact on their self-perceived competence and confidence to navigate a new domain outside of their athletic life. Likewise, being aware of their transferable skills might provide an important pathway for the improvement of the student-athletes' career adaptability and career development. The intervention targets to engage the student-athletes on self and career exploration exercises that will measure a student-athlete's familiarity with transferable skills, help them identify what skills are most transferable, and provide them with practical exercises that will enable application of these skills until they gain an increase in clarity and confidence to transition. Overall, it is hoped that through the intervention, student-athletes will be able to discover that the skills set that they have learned, refined, practiced under the pressure of training and competition can be the cornerstone of success in their potential careers outside of their sport. Their resume may not contain a long list of internships or jobs, the context of learning might be different from their non-athlete peers, but the skills, work habits, attitudes and abilities they practice as student athletes are aligned with the foundations of excellence in the workplace.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

A. Career Dilemmas of Collegiate Student-Athletes

It has been observed in the literature that collegiate student-athletes frequently lag in career development; they progress more slowly in this aspect than their non-athlete peers (Shurts and Shoffner, 2004). They are often behind their non-athlete peers in terms of critical career readiness factors such as self-exploration and assessment of their personal interests, skills, and inherent traits and tendencies (Petitpas et al., 1997). Research generally suggests that participation in collegiate sports contributes a lot to the physical and personal development of an individual. However, it has also been shown that this

participation can lead to difficulties for the student-athlete especially in their career development process. Opportunities to explore career options may be more limited for student-athletes because of training and competition schedules. The rigorous time demands, lack of clear role models, and narrow range of life experiences are but a few of the reasons cited for the student-athletes' slow career development (Sorensen, 2013). Majority of them lack the traditional work experience such as internships due to obligations in their sport thus they are unable to develop the confidence in job application processes (Samuels, 2002). Additionally, the confidence of student-athletes on their career readiness is rooted on how they perceive their workplace competence; and according to Cornelius (1995, as cited in Rhomberg, 2021), Murphy et al. (1996, as cited in Rhomberg, 2021), and NCAA (2016, as cited in Rhomberg, 2021) there is a deficit in positive self-perception of student-athletes on their workplace competence. Results of the study made by Espina (2014) among student-athletes reported that the commonly expressed vocational need of this population is to be equipped with relevant career information both in terms of course options (i.e. major) while in college and the career opportunities for them after graduation. They also expressed concern about their inability to set clear career goals and the lack of specific career plans. A number expressed the need to develop other competencies or job skills in addition to their athletic skills. The results clearly indicate that collegiate student-athletes have a strong need to acquire the career information necessary for planning and goal-setting, explore their career options outside of their sport and develop the skills necessary for employment. Perhaps the amount of time they devote to training and competition often win out over career preparation leaving student-athletes unprepared for life after sport. Similarly, NCAA (2016) tallied that 64% of female and 49% of male student-athletes selected "preparation for a career after college" as the top topic they wish their coaches or athletic administrators talked more about. Moreover, most student-athletes are concerned about the termination of their athletic careers after college; at times it is likened to fear of losing a significant relationship (Espina, 2014). They may have identified themselves too much in their athlete roles eventually causing them to have an unclear vision of the availability of more career options other than playing their sports (Williams, 2010). This condition is commonly described in literature as identity foreclosure or the state in which the athlete rigidly commits to a role without considering or exploring alternatives (Shurts and Shoffner, 2004). They have become so dedicated to their sport that they missed out on a lot of learning opportunities where they could have found a different role outside of their sport. The tendency to be socially isolated from the rest of the student population might have contributed to their failure to explore other roles outside of being an athlete. These individuals lived, ate, studied, and interacted almost exclusively with their fellow student-athletes. In addition to identity foreclosure, researchers have also found that a strong athletic identity may slow down the career development of student-athletes (Lally and Kerr, 2013). High athletic identity has been associated as well with decreased career planning for life after college, lower levels of career adaptability and decreased career maturity (Murphy et al., 1996; Tyrance et al., 2013). Moreover, athletes have reported difficulties dealing with situations in non-athletic domains and delayed identity shifts because of a lack in non-athletic life experiences during their athletic careers (Park, Lavellee, & Tod, 2013).

Keeping in mind that many student-athletes transition into non-sport careers after graduating, it is worth noting that student-athletes can still be career ready if they will build on their awareness on the transferable skills they possess to prepare them for career shifts (August, 2020, as cited in Migliaccio, 2023). Although studies have shown the importance of the awareness of athletes' transferable skills, Migliaccio (2023) finds that student-athletes face a dilemma on whether or not they do have transferable skills. Additionally, it is a common occurrence for student-athletes to overlook their transferable skills and feel lost on how to apply these skills in domains outside of athletics (Van Raalte et al., 2017). They often fail to recognize the skills they've acquired and mastered through their athletic participation and how those skills can be relevant to the workplace.

B. Transferable Skills Gained Through Sports

Aside from a career in the field of sports as professional athletes, there are various circumstances and opportunities that may prompt student-athletes to pursue and transition into careers in other fields. A measurement of how frequent this career transition occurs is the National Collegiate Athletic Association's (NCAA) (2024, as cited in Pierce et al., 2024) statistic which reports that around 97% of its student-athletes transition out of sports once they have completed their undergraduate studies. One notable factor that contributes to the aforementioned transition is the confidence level of these athletes after realizing and gaining transferable skills during their stint as student-athletes (Menke & Germany, 2018, as cited in Pryor & Ross-Stewart, 2024). It is noteworthy that when athletes realize they already have the transferable skills and traits which are beneficial for success in non-athletic areas, they feel more capable and confident in pursuing those areas (Petitpas et al., 1997). Bolles (1992, as cited in Shiina et al., 2003) defines transferable skills as skills that are applicable to different

domains and fields and are deemed necessary in a vast range of situations both inside and outside of work (Wiant, 1977, as cited in, Brennan, 2024). Nägele & Stalder (2016) further describe these skills to be non-technical skills that are often seen and used in any social setting of everyday life such as problem-solving and communication. Some examples of transferable skills are listed in a study by Rosenberg et al. (2012, as cited in Nägele & Stalder, 2016), namely: basic literacy, logical thinking, critical thinking, leadership and managerial aptitude, and interpersonal communication. Brennan (2024) also lists creativity, problem-solving, and time management as examples of transferable skills. These life skills are highly valued in one's career journey as industries continue to evolve and the number of settings an individual needs to adapt to continues to increase (Hodge and Danish, 1999, as cited in Samuels, 2002). Moreover, transferable skills allow individuals to confidently and effectively switch behaviors as necessary depending on the setting they are in (Samuels, 2002). According to Danish, Petitpas, and Hale (1993, as cited in Samuels, 2002), transferable skills can be learned through a perpetual process of demonstration, modeling, and practice. In the modern age where the workforce is highly competitive, scholars and employers have given other labels for transferable skills to emphasize its importance in one's career development, namely: core competencies, core proficiencies, generic skills, and personal competencies (Kemp & Seagraves, 1995; Nägele & Stalder, 2016 as cited in Brennan, 2024). With this notion in mind, it can be said that transferable skills are influential factors in an individual's employability and value in the workforce (Nägele & Stalder, 2016). Chan et al., (2017, as cited in Brennan, 2024) reports that there is a demand for higher educational institutions to integrate the development of transferable skills into their curricula in addition to assessing students for these skills. This information implies the high importance of transferable skills in different aspects of life, especially in terms of one's professional advancement and career development.

In the context of sports, transferable skills manifest in an abstract nature and are adopted by athletes while exposing themselves in the sporting environment (Mayocchi & Hanrahan, 2000, as cited in Rhomberg, 2021). An example of transferable skills in athletics would be self-discipline as mentioned by Woods (2017). He elaborated that self-discipline helps an athlete develop specific skills during athletic activities such as scoring accuracy and consistency; but aside from this, self-discipline is also applicable to specific skills in the workplace like promptness and strong work ethic. In a study conducted by Samuels (2002) which involved eight focus groups of student-athletes, a transferable skill developed by these athletes was teamwork which encompasses a variety of interpersonal skills such as working with diverse personalities, achieving both personal and team goals, and conflict resolution (Samuels, 2002). Aside from teamwork, another transferable skill that was identified is perspective taking, which includes priority balancing, response control, and decision making (Samuels, 2002). To illustrate an example of transferable skills developed in athletics, Mayocchi and Hanrahan (2000) cited a college athlete with little or no job experience at all but can consistently deliver during games using a variety of skills such as self-motivation to improve one's game, being focused on accomplishing one's goals, handling pressure, having confidence and mental toughness. These skills that allow the athlete to deliver accurately and consistently during games can be the same skills set that can be key to surviving a competitive career in a work environment. In a quantitative study conducted by Woods (2017), student-athletes ranked several skills that they deem transferable from most to least with the notable skills being time management, ability to handle pressure, goal-orientedness, mental toughness, and confidence. In other studies, it is found that commitment and perseverance are also transferable skills developed by athletes both through their own experiences and through the help of external factors like their coaches, teammates, and families (Woods, 2017). In a study conducted by the NCAA GOALS (2016), student-athletes reflected on and evaluated skills or qualities they believe are most transferable, marketable, and influential from their experience as a student-athlete. The skills and qualities highlighted include personal responsibility, teamwork, work ethic, leadership, personal values and ethics, self-confidence, time management, understanding of other races, study skills, and commitment to volunteerism. Furthermore, a number of authors posited that athletic participation could facilitate the formation of skills in areas such as leadership, communication, teamwork, self-motivation, and organization (Mayocchi & Hanrahan, 2000; Petitpas et al., 1997; Petitpas et al., 2004, Van Raalte et al., 2017). The value of student-athletes' transferable skills are not only recognized by scholars and players in the domain of sports, but they are recognized by employers across different industries as well. Chalfin et al. (2015, as cited in Woods, 2017) look into the employer's perspective on student-athletes' transferable skills and employability, wherein they find that employers find student-athletes more attractive and well-suited for entry-level roles because of the transferable skills they develop during their sports careers. Employers desire a competitive nature, a goal-oriented mindset, the ability to work in a team, and a coachable mindset when looking for a competent candidate; and the aforementioned transferable skills were identified by employers as skills present in student-athletes (Chalfin et al., 2015, as cited in Woods, 2017). Furthermore, some employers and recruiters that participated in the study conducted by Chalfin et al. (2015, as cited in Woods, 2017) view the role of being a student-athlete as a full time job since the time and effort given by student-athletes

to their respective sports can be translated into the possible time and effort they may give to a company's work environment. In addition, they see that student-athletes have transferable skills that have been ingrained in their characters because they did not just learn these skills, they have refined them and practiced them with the kind of passion that drives their teams to victories. Indeed, there are numerous skills that student-athletes acquired through their sport which can be transferable to non-sport related jobs. Educating the student-athletes on being self-aware of these skills is critical in order for them to feel confident navigating non-athletic careers and be able to improve their ability to utilize their skills in different work settings and life domains as well.

C. Support and Interventions to Increase Awareness of Transferable Skills

There has been a growing need for interventions for athletes when they exit from sport and transition into new careers. However, research still shows that the biggest barrier for student-athletes adjusting from a sport to a non-sport career is their lack of awareness of their sport-transferable skills (August, 2020). It is often implied in literature that when athletes go through the transition process, it is critical for them to be aware of their strengths which were developed through their sport, and they must feel capable of expressing those strengths to a potential employer. A growing body of research demonstrates the positive effects associated with athletes' awareness of their transferable skills (Danish et al., 1993; Mayocchi & Hanrahan, 2000; Petitpas et al., 1997; Petitpas et al., 2004; Van Raalte et al., 2017). Petitpas et al. (2024) opined that when student-athletes increase their awareness that their athletic participation is a source of learning opportunities to develop transferable skills, it gives them confidence that they have a competitive advantage in the job marketplace. Van Raalte and colleagues (2017) found through a self and career exploration workshop for student-athletes that those who discovered what transferable skills they possess while in college were more confident in their future career pursuits. Sauer and colleagues (2013) saw that athletes scored higher in transferable skills such as mentoring and emotional management compared to non-athletes, and those athletes then secured high paying jobs. Furthermore, the study of Shaw (2024) found that awareness of transferable skills has a positive impact on the student-athletes' performance in academics, athletics and career confidence as well. Findings from the study of NCAA (2016) conclude that a vital place to start for athletic staff and coaches in the holistic development of student-athlete is to provide programs and learning opportunities for this population to develop more awareness of transferable skills, the value of building upon them, and learning how to best market those skills in the process of transitioning from college athletics to a non-athletic career setting.

There are several programs, initiatives, methods, interventions, and other kinds of support that brought more awareness to student-athletes' transferable skills and yielded positive results in student-athletes' career development. One of which is a transferable skills workshops conducted by Shiina et al. (2003) wherein the researchers found that participating in these kinds of activities enhanced student-athletes' beliefs, perception, and confidence in their career development journey. During the said workshops, Shiina et al. (2003) made student-athletes participate in activities that identified transferable skills they have developed in their sport and translated these skills into the domains of other careers. These activities were proven to be effective through higher results in these athletes' Career Decision Self-Efficacy post-test scores compared to their pre-test scores (Shiina et al., 2003). Another study that illustrates the efficacy of transferable skills support would be one by Shaw (2024) wherein a psychological skills training was conducted. The methods Shaw (2024) implemented in the training consisted of goal setting and imagery activities, self-talk, and self-regulation, and these methods aimed to foster and bring awareness to student-athletes' transferable skills of self-motivation, work ethic, and goal-orientedness. It was reported that student-athletes who underwent the training discovered that being aware of their mental transferable skills and further honing these skills resulted in positive character development, namely: improved self-esteem, higher academic standing, improved relationships, and bigger confidence in their careers (Shaw, 2024). To further showcase the efficacy of bringing awareness to student-athletes' transferable skills through different support systems, the repeated exposure of student-athletes to experiences—both inside and outside of sports—that allow them to systematically practice their transferable skills was found to positively influence a student-athlete's career readiness (Migliaccio, 2023). Woods (2017) finds in her study that one's support system such as family, coaches, athletics department were able to bring awareness of transferable skills to student-athletes through sharing of personal experiences, education, dialogues, and consultations with the said support systems. In relation to the exposure of student-athletes to situations that require them to use transferable skills, both studies by Migliaccio (2023) and Woods (2017) report that this exposure and these interactions with support systems results into a positive impact on a student-athlete's job success because of the recognition of and confidence in their transferable skills.

Currently, there are institutions and individuals who have come up with different interventions to help support the development of student-athletes' transferable skills and promote awareness of these transferable skills. These interventions range from seminars and talks, wherein student-athletes learn about transferable skills through traditional classroom-type learning, to service-learning projects, wherein student-athletes learn through experiential learning. One example of an intervention that follows more traditional methods would be the creation and distribution of handouts as proposed by Kastler (2021). She conceptualized and distributed handouts discussing career development with student-athletes and other stakeholders as the target audience through career centers, social media, and through career counseling offices and tackles the following concepts regarding career development: (1) barriers faced by student-athletes, (2) articulating student-athlete experiences in resumes and job interviews, and (3) identity development of student-athletes and its importance. Aside from the distribution of handouts, another example of an intervention that adopts the traditional method of learning would be developing educational support models. The Success Model developed by Titlebaum, Stankovich, and Meeker is one model that illustrates this intervention. The Success Model is an educational model that was designed to capitalize and utilize student-athletes' transferable skills in improving their academic performance and prepare them for careers outside of sports (Titlebaum et al., 2000). The model focuses on student-athletes' self-management, study habits, and career resources and how these components of their academics could be maximized and integrated in regular study hall sessions and workshops throughout the academic year. The model is not meant to replace existing university curricula but rather support student-athletes in adapting to their respective curricula. According to Titlebaum et al. (2000) this model takes inspiration from two similar older educational models, namely: (1) Stier's (1992, as cited in Titlebaum et al., 2000) Triad Assisting, Advising, and Assessment Model which is designed to meet the academic, personal, social, and athletic needs of student-athletes through proactive methods; and (2) Peer Mentoring Programs which are adopted by several universities in the United States of America in which junior and senior student-athletes are tasked to mentor freshman and sophomore student-athletes. Moving on to interventions that focus on experiential learning, an example of this would be campus involvement opportunities. This intervention was developed by Kastler (2021) to complement the other interventions of her project that focus on more traditional learning. Campus involvement opportunities will allow student-athletes to gather more experience in dealing with scenarios outside of sports since they normally do not have enough opportunities to gather such experiences due to conflicts in schedule and commitments (Navarro et al., 2020, as cited in Kastler, 2021). In this intervention, Kastler (2021) mentions that career centers and offices must reach out and collaborate with university offices, coaches, athletic departments, and external relations (i.e. partner companies, employer relations, and service-learning centers).

III. CONCLUSION

A. Theoretical Model

The model that will guide the conceptualization of a career intervention for student-athletes is the Life Development Intervention (LDI) model by Danish, Petitpas and Hale (1993) who advocate for the principle that growth and change are necessary for human development. The authors recognize that there are critical life events that may prompt an athlete to transition out of sports, and it is where the utilization of their transferable skills for continued growth and successful adaptation to a new setting will be relevant. Given the number of factors that may influence the process of transition, Danish et al. (1993) supports the notion that athletes who prepare for a career shift and make good use of their acquired transferable skills are more likely to adapt successfully to any new experience outside of their athletic career. The LDI model identified a three-step process in which counselors can help influence athletes to recognize their goals, potential, skills and ability to thrive and utilize transferable skills in a non-athletic career setting. The first step requires athletes to identify skills and traits that they develop through sports and boost awareness and confidence that these skills are valuable or transferable in other settings or domains of their life. In the second step, it is essential that athletes develop an understanding of why and how they learned the skills in a sport context. Once an athlete has recognized that the skills they possess resulted from their athletic experiences (e.g. training, competitions, victories, failures, trial and error, and continuous feedback in sport), they can then be led to identifying settings out of sport where they have utilized those same skills. This process can help the athlete prepare for the third step of transferring skill from one domain to another. In the third step, athletes can be helped to focus more on their perceived level of the skills they have already identified and possess, help them build on these skills and strengths, and prepare them with specific ways on how they can apply transferable skills to a more specific setting which is a career in a non-athletic setting. They should be assisted in seeking out sources of social support, resources and venues that will recognize their potential outside of sport.

B. Intervention Framework

The framework below outlines the focus of the intervention being proposed. It describes the perceived concern of student-athletes that needs to be addressed, what intervention can be used to address it and the expected outcomes from the intervention that will be provided.

Figure 1. Intervention framework

C. Proposed Contents of the Intervention

The intervention's content will be directed towards addressing the perceived main concern of student-athletes, which is the lack of awareness regarding the transferable skills that they have developed as a result of sport participation and how they can be utilized when they transition into a non-sport career setting. It will focus on creating awareness of the skills that they possess, increasing their confidence that these skills make them career-ready, and identifying resources and learning opportunities that can help them solidify the transferable skills that they've gained through their sport. Over-all, the intervention will ensure that student-athletes will develop confidence that they are as career-ready and as employable as their non-athlete peers.

1. The intervention will include developing modules that will contain structured learning exercises on self-exploration and career exploration specifically targeting the identification of transferable skills learned through their sport and facilitating the awareness and transfer of these skills to other career-related domains. The modules will be delivered through a series of workshops and/or learning sessions per team or per sporting event.
2. Student-athletes will be asked to complete the Transferable Skills Inventory, a tool to measure how their sport participation contributed to their skill development. It will help identify the highest-scoring transferable skills and the applicability of these skills to specific job requirements or the type of tasks in which those skills can be of relevant use. Individualized feedback giving will also be done for a more personal discussion of the assessment results.
3. A focus group discussion with former student-athletes who are already employed in a non-athletic career setting will be organized to discuss how successfully they are able to navigate the world of work using the skills they developed through their athletic participation. The session will be recorded for viewing purposes of the intervention participants.
4. Participants will also be exposed to different career events at the university (e.g. job fairs, career talks, company orientations, internships, volunteer programs) that will allow them to see how their transferable skills align with the skills needed for their occupations of interest. Opportunities for internships and volunteer work will also be explored and presented to the participants. Occupational handbooks, pamphlets, handouts, and other resource materials that will elaborate on job postings, job descriptions, required skills, and available training programs will also be provided to the participants to enable curiosity and confidence building.

5. Personal barriers or difficulties being experienced by the student-athletes in identifying their skills and in developing the confidence to transition will also be addressed through the conduct of individual career counseling sessions. Career mentoring may also be done in areas such as how to articulate their strengths and transferable skills to their prospective employers.

IV. IMPLICATIONS

1. Student-athletes should develop a deeper appreciation of the usefulness of transferable skills not just to their career but also to their academic and personal life.
2. Transferable skills discovered may increase the capacity and confidence of student-athletes to develop their own career plan and set their career goals and direction.
3. The proposed intervention can prosper into a more collaborative and integrated approach by including the coaching staff and other athletic staff as resource for highlighting the skills that are transferable in the world of work. A conscious effort to elaborate them in their training programs and daily dialogues with student-athletes will aid in the smooth understanding of how athletic skills can be converted into job skills.
4. The proposed intervention can be a springboard for the discovery and exploration of other factors that might have an impact on the career readiness of student-athletes.
5. The proposed intervention forwards the importance of taking care of a student-athlete's career development for a successful transition out of their sport. A career program that will allow student-athletes to be actively engaged in their career development process should be formulated for this unique population.

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